

NATURALISTIC-SCIENTIFIC PICTURE OF THE WORLD IN POST- NONCLASSICAL ERA OF SCIENCE

Pardayev Sultunmurod

The 2nd year Doctoral Researcher at the National University of Uzbekistan
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Annotation. The article seeks to reveal the main aspects and epistemological uniqueness of the natural-scientific view of the world in the post-nonclassical period. Furthermore, it highlights the impact of the world natural-scientific landscape on the development of science. The important aspect of this article is that the current philosophical aspects of the development of science are revealed from the scientific point of view.

Key words: microphysics, quantum mechanics, post-nonclassical, quantum mechanical landscape, superconductivity, radioactive rays, photons, photoelectric effect, theory of relativity.

According to the analysis of the literature, by the 20th century, the natural-scientific landscape of the world began to be explained on the basis of microphysics or quantum mechanics in understanding its ontological uniqueness. In addition, a new stage in the development of science begins in the 20th century. The science of this period is called post-nonclassical, because at the threshold of this century, a revolution occurs in science, as a result of which it begins to differ significantly from the classical science of the previous period. In fact, the process of the second scientific revolution is taking place in the natural-scientific view of the world, that is, the relativistic and quantum mechanical view of the world is emerging. From this point of view, electromagnetic waves by H. Hertz, X-rays by Roentgen, phenomenon of radioactivity by M. Becquerel, element of radium by M. Sklodovskaya and P. Curie, first theory of quantum theory by M. Planck and others can be explained by the creation of a number of discoveries. As a result of these discoveries, the physical landscape of the world will change historically.

If before Maxwell, physical existence was thought to be in the form of material points, then it was considered that physical existence consists of continuous fields that cannot be explained from the point of view of mechanics. In the 20th century, a new era has entered, the physical landscape of the Universe has turned into a fundamentally new realist and quantum mechanical landscape. That is why, by this time, based on scientific theories and discoveries made by scientists, the concept of the indivisibility of the atom has been proved to be wrong. In particular, the formation processes of quantum mechanics began in the physics of this period. In fact, quantum mechanics is a branch of physics that

expresses the laws of motion of micro-particles in certain external fields. In particular, quantum mechanics is helping to understand the properties of solids, phenomena such as superconductivity and fluidity.

In particular, the great Russian scientist N.E. It is necessary to mention Zhukovsky (1847-1921). Among other things, he conducted his scientific activity in the field of theoretical mechanics at higher educational institutions in Moscow. N. Bibitov writes: "Zhukovsky believed that a teacher who lectures on theoretical mechanics should definitely lead practical training."

Indeed, according to him, a person who wants to learn real mechanics: solves concrete problems of mechanics; learning the specific characteristics of things in their own state; it is necessary to be based on analysis and geometry. From this point of view, he takes into account that if the mechanical side of any phenomenon is expressed, its essence becomes understandable. At the same time, he develops several different geometric solutions to mechanical problems.

According to our analysis, it is no exaggeration to say that A.Einstein's theory of relativity was a real revolution in the natural-scientific landscape of the world. Because it is from his proof of the theory of relativity that the era of non-classical science begins in the world of science. Including, according to N. Shermukhamedova: "Einstein creates the mathematical theory of Brownian motion, develops the quantum concept of light and interprets Lobachevsky's geometry from the point of view of physics." The special theory of relativity of relativistic mechanics is based on its following two postulates:

- 1) The principle of constancy of the speed of light: the speed of light in a vacuum (c) is constant in all inertial reference systems and does not depend on the movement of sources and return devices;
- 2) The principle of relativity: it is impossible to determine whether this system is at rest or in motion with any physical (mechanical, electrical, optical) experiments conducted in an inertial frame of reference, that is, the laws of physics are the same in all inertial frame of reference.

From the above analytical postulates, it can be said that relativistic mechanics does not deny the laws of classical mechanics, which have existed until now, but on the contrary, it is necessary to mention that it shows the limits of its application. If we look at it from this point of view, according to his point of view, he emphasizes that no body in the nature that surrounds us can move at a speed equal to the speed of light. In addition, it proves that the speed of all moving objects on Earth is zero compared to the speed of light.

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